

Sensitivity of SAR data to post-fire forest regrowth in Mediterranean and boreal forests

Mihai Tanase⁽¹⁾, Juan de la Riva⁽¹⁾, Maurizio Santoro⁽²⁾, Eric Kasischke⁽³⁾ and Fernando Pérez-Cabello⁽¹⁾

⁽¹⁾ University of Zaragoza, Pedro Cerbuna 12, 50009, Zaragoza (Spain), Email:

mihai.tanase@tma.ro

⁽²⁾ Gamma Remote Sensing, Worbstrasse 225, CH-3073 Gümligen (Switzerland)

⁽³⁾ University of Maryland, 2181 LeFrack Hall, College Park, MD 20742 (USA)

Abstract

Disturbed forests may need decades to reach mature stage and optical based vegetation indices are usually poorly suited for monitoring purposes due to the rapid saturation of the signal with increasing canopy cover. Spaceborne synthetic aperture radar (SAR) data provide instead better monitoring opportunities since the scattered waves are more sensitive to the vegetation structure. Images from two test sites in Spain and Alaska have been used to analyze SAR metrics (backscatter and interferometric coherence) from regrowing forests previously affected by fire. TerraSAR-X X-band backscatter showed the lowest sensitivity to forest regrowth, the average backscatter increasing by 1-2 dB between the most recent fire scar and the unburned forest. Envisat Advanced Synthetic Aperture (ASAR) C-band backscatter showed increased sensitivity, (around 4 dB). The Advanced Land Observing Satellite (ALOS) Phased Array-type L-band Synthetic Aperture Radar (PALSAR) L-band backscatter presented the highest sensitivity to forest regrowth (approximately 8 dB). For a given frequency the sensitivity of the SAR backscatter to forest regrowth varied with local incidence angle and polarization. The interferometric coherence showed low sensitivity to forest regrowth at all SAR frequencies. For Mediterranean forests five phases of forest regrowth were discerned whereas for boreal forest, up to four different regrowth phases could be discerned with L-band SAR data. In comparison, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) provided reliable differentiation only for the most recent development stages. The results obtained were consistent in both environments.

I. Introduction

Information on forest post fire regrowth is of great interest for many agencies dealing with environmental issues (e.g. carbon budget, forest management, etc.) since forests need long time to reach the biomass level, structure and carbon sink capacity prior to the fire event. Satellite imagery covers large regions and the temporal recurrence of the data collection facilitates the temporal analysis of wide areas. Fire impacts and subsequent processes may be identified and monitored by means of remote sensing using optical (Marchetti et al. 1995; Patterson and Yool 1998; Viedma et

37 al. 1997), radar (Bourgeau-Chavez et al. 1997; Bourgeau-Chavez et al. 2002; Ruecker and Siegert
38 2000; Siegert and Ruecker 2000) or lidar (Goetz et al. 2010) sensors. Suitability of remote sensing
39 data for monitoring post-fire vegetation development is determined by two factors: a) sensitivity to
40 alterations in the radiometric response to wildfire-induced changes and post disturbance vegetation
41 development and b) the spatial resolution of satellite imagery which allows the characterization of
42 the response patterns.

43 Disappearance of charcoal-ash remains, increase of vegetation and the subsequent decrease of
44 bare soil cover are targets for remote sensing satellites operating in the visible and infrared region of
45 the electromagnetic spectrum. In consequence of such dynamics, infrared reflectance increase and
46 red and blue reflectance decrease caused by changes in chlorophyll levels are detected by optical
47 sensors. A number of studies evidenced this as useful for post-fire vegetation monitoring (Díaz-
48 Delgado and Pons 2001; Henry and Hope 1998; Pérez-Cabello 2002; Wagtendonk et al. 2004). The
49 Normalized Different Vegetation Index (NDVI) (Rouse et al. 1973) has been the most frequently
50 used tool for monitoring, analyzing, and mapping temporal and spatial post-fire variations (Díaz-
51 Delgado et al. 2003; Díaz-Delgado et al. 2002; Viedma et al. 1997). However, NDVI responds more
52 to changes in leaf area than to changes in overall biomass (Henry and Hope 1998) and its relation to
53 leaf area index (LAI) varies both intra and inter-annually reaching saturation levels at high LAI
54 values (Wang et al. 2005). Therefore, tracking post fire vegetation development using NDVI is
55 usually limited to the first decade after fire. The analysis of post-fire vegetation condition of an oak
56 forest in NE Spain showed that pre-fire NDVI values were reached after only 7 years (Díaz-Delgado
57 and Pons 2001). Similar trends were found by (Clemente et al. 2009; Vila and Barbosa 2010) in
58 other Mediterranean regions whereas in boreal forests pre-fire NDVI values were reached after 13
59 years (Cuevas-Gonzalez et al. 2009).

60 Forests may need decades to reach the mature stage and the short period within which optical
61 based vegetation indices reach pre-fire levels implies limited value for regrowth monitoring. SAR
62 data have the potential to significantly extend the monitoring period since the backscattered signal is
63 directly influenced by the forest structure. Backscatter sensitivity to forest structural parameters
64 increases with the increase of wavelength. Typically, the backscatter coefficient increases with
65 forest biomass reaching saturation as a function of forest type and structure. Increased sensitivity to
66 forest regrowth was reported for L-band HH polarization compared to C-band VV polarization for a
67 ten year old fire scar in China (Sun et al. 2002). The longer L-band wavelength allowed the
68 differentiation among young (i.e. post-fire regrowth) and mature forest stands. In a Mediterranean

69 environment temporal changes in forest biomass were assessed using multi-temporal C-band VV
70 polarized images in order to characterize post-fire processes (Minchella et al. 2009). Furthermore,
71 interferometric coherence could provide additional information for burned area monitoring. Repeat-
72 pass interferometric coherence is usually low over mature forests and increases significantly for
73 areas covered by short vegetation or bare soil (Wegmuller and Werner 1995). In forests affected by
74 fire C- and L-band co-polarized coherence was found to increase with respect to unburned areas
75 (Liew et al. 1999; Takeuchi and Yamada 2002).

76 Previous studies on post-fire forest monitoring were largely carried out using optical based
77 indices. The few studies on regrowth monitoring carried out using SAR data did not take advantage
78 of the more sensitive cross-polarized backscatter nor systematically evaluated the sensitivity of
79 backscatter and coherence at different wavelengths and polarizations to forest regrowth in burned
80 areas. Cross-polarized data is more sensitive to forest structure (Dobson et al. 1992b; Rignot et al.
81 1994; Toan et al. 1992) and could provide better differentiation between recovery stages of
82 disturbed forests. In areas recently affected by fires the properties of X- C- and L-band backscatter
83 and interferometric coherence at different polarizations has been thoroughly discussed in (Tanase et
84 al. 2010b; Tanase et al. 2010c) for the Mediterranean region. This study focused on the post-fire
85 dynamic assessment using similar SAR datasets. More specifically, we evaluated X-, C- and L-band
86 backscatter and interferometric coherence and inferred the utility of these metrics for post-fire
87 regrowth monitoring in Mediterranean forests. In addition, regrowth in boreal forests affected by fire
88 was studied using L-band data. The sensitivity of SAR measurements to regrowth is then compared
89 to trends in the NDVI metric obtained from optical images acquired over the study sites.

90 II. Study sites

91 Two sites located in the Mediterranean and the boreal zone were considered. The first site
92 (Zuera) was located in central Ebro valley, northeastern Spain and has a Mediterranean climate with
93 continental features and marked seasonal variation of precipitations. The area is characterized by a
94 hilly relief, elevations ranging from 400 m to 750 m above sea level. The topography is moderate,
95 around 65% of the surface presenting slopes smaller than 15°. Aleppo pine forests (*Pinus halepensis*
96 L.) cover approximately 22,000 hectares being interspersed with shrub vegetation and cereal crops.
97 The vegetation is xerophilous, drought resistant and highly flammable providing abundant fuels.
98 The forest has a homogeneous structure. The average height is approximately 6.5 m and the average
99 biomass around 45 tons/ha. Old stands reach heights of 12-13 m and 90 tons/ha (Notivol et al.
100 2005). During the last century the site has been repeatedly affected by fires, some areas having been

101 burned up to three times. Sixteen fires larger than 10 ha were identified using Landsat MSS and TM
102 imagery which was also used for digitizing the fire perimeters. The year of burn was cross-checked
103 with information obtained from the Regional Environmental Service of Aragón which also provided
104 the perimeters of the oldest burns (1922 and 1952). The year of burn and the affected area are
105 presented in **Table 1**. Aleppo pine regenerates abundantly after fire due to the large seed bank stored
106 in the canopy (Tapias et al. 2001) from relatively young forest age (15 years). Post fire succession in
107 Aleppo pine forests involves stand self-replacement (Buhk et al. 2006) (e.g., shrubs dominated by
108 *Quercus coccifera* and immature pines followed by mature pine forest with a dense understory
109 layer). In areas repeatedly affected by fire the vegetation is dominated by shrub species and the
110 succession to forest needs considerably longer time. Previous studies suggested no clear relationship
111 between seedling density and burn severity. However, seedling growth was higher in areas affected
112 by high burn severities (Pausas et al. 2002). The minimum human intervention and the vigorous
113 forest recovery at Zuera site due to the specific microclimate of the area and the resilience of *Pinus*
114 *halepensis* L. forest allowed almost ideal condition for the forest regeneration.

115 The boreal site was located in interior Alaska near Delta Junction. In this region, the average
116 annual temperature is -2.1 °C, with the warmest month being July (15.6 °C) and the coldest January
117 (-19.7 °C). Average annual precipitation is 290 mm, with three-quarters of this amount occurring
118 during the growing season (May to September). Twenty fires were identified using information
119 provided by the Alaska Interagency Coordination Center. The year of burn and the surface affected
120 by fire are presented in **Table 1**. The fires were mostly located on a gently sloping alluvial outwash
121 plane north of the Alaska Range, with elevations ranging between 300 and 600 m, and slopes being
122 less than 3° . A detailed description of the site can be found in (Kasischke and Johnstone 2005). The
123 upland forests at the Alaskan sites are undergoing secondary succession following fires, where
124 poorly drained soils are occupied by black spruce *Picea mariana* Mill. forests on cooler, wetter sites
125 and *Picea glauca* (Moench) forests on warmer drier sites (Viereck et al. 1983). Post fire succession
126 in *Picea mariana* forests involves self replacement (e.g., shrubs to immature spruce/shrub mixture
127 followed by mature forests), while relay floristics occur after fire on sites occupied by *Picea glauca*
128 forests (shrubs following by *Populus* sp. or *Betula* sp. forests followed by mixed deciduous/spruce
129 forests followed by mature *Picea glauca* forests). Throughout this paper we considered the terms
130 “forest age” and “years since burn” as interchangeable since the first seedlings appear during the
131 following spring after the fire event.

132 III. Earth Observation and ancillary data

133 For the Zuera site, the SAR dataset consisted of images acquired by the TerraSAR-X (TSX),
134 Environmental Satellite (Envisat) Advanced SAR (ASAR) and Advanced Land Observing Satellite
135 (ALOS) Phased Array type L-band SAR (PALSAR) sensors. For the Delta Junction site, only
136 ALOS PALSAR data were available. **Table 2** presents the acquisition dates together with the main
137 characteristics of the datasets. TerraSAR-X dual-polarized (HH and HV) images were acquired in
138 strip map mode (SM). One Envisat ASAR dual-polarized (HH and HV) image was acquired in
139 Alternating Polarization mode (AP) whereas the two images used for interferometric processing
140 were acquired in Image Mode (IM) at HH polarization. ALOS PALSAR data were acquired in full
141 polarimetric (PLR) and dual polarization (HH and HV) Fine Beam Dual (FBD) modes. For the
142 Zuera site, backscatter measurements (HH and HV polarization) were available for similar incidence
143 angle for all sensors whereas the incidence angle of the image pairs used for interferometric
144 coherence analysis were either 23° (ASAR) or 40° (TSX).

145 The SAR data for the Zuera site were absolutely calibrated, multi-looked to obtain the desired 25
146 m spatial resolution and geocoded to Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) projection using a 20 m
147 spatial resolution digital elevation model (DEM). The DEM was obtained from the regional
148 government of Aragón. Topographic normalization of the backscatter to account for the effect of
149 varying incidence angle from near to far range and the effective pixel area was applied (Ulander
150 1996). The resulting images were in gamma nought (γ^0) format, and only included variations of the
151 scattering properties of a target due to local orientation. Coherence generation consisted in co-
152 registration of the images, spatial multi-look, common band filtering and differential
153 interferogram computation, coherence estimation and geocoding to UTM projection. Detailed
154 description of the processing is given in (Tanase et al. 2010b) and (Tanase et al. 2010c).

155 The PALSAR dataset for the Delta Junction sites was processed in a similar way. The images
156 were geocoded to 30 m using a 60 m spatial resolution DEM and UTM projection. The National
157 Elevation Dataset (NED) from US Geological Survey (USGS) was used. Although most of the area
158 presented flat or nearly flat topography, normalization of the backscatter was applied in order to
159 obtain similar metrics (γ^0) as for the Zuera site.

160 **Fig. 1** shows the coherence image product (red: coherence; green: backscatter, blue: backscatter
161 ratio) for the ALOS PALSAR FBD image pairs acquired over Zuera and Delta Junction sites. Fire
162 perimeters together with the burn year were superimposed over the satellite images. The coherence
163 image product show the selected fires in red and orange because of overall high coherence and low
164 backscatter. Forests appear in green tones (high backscatter and low coherence) at Delta Junction

165 whereas at Zuera they appear in yellow tones (high backscatter and high coherence). The large
166 difference in forest coherence values for the two sites was explained by the more stable weather
167 conditions at the Zuera sites and the greater stiffness of the L-band scatterers in Mediterranean pine
168 forests. Red colors correspond to sparsely vegetated areas which did not change (high coherence and
169 low backscatter) whereas blue colors represent areas of considerable backscatter change between
170 image acquisitions.

171 Two Landsat images (one for each site) acquired on 2008.08.22 (Zuera) and 2009.08.12 (Delta
172 Junction) were used to estimate the NDVI in the fire affected areas and compare it to the SAR
173 metrics (backscatter and coherence). The Landsat images were transformed to the same coordinate
174 system used to geocode the SAR data. Both images underwent radiometric corrections to
175 compensate for variations in sensor radiometric response, sun angle, sun azimuth and topography.
176 Raw digital number (DN) values were converted to satellite reflectance.

177 To aid the interpretation, meteorological data collected from the nearest available meteorological
178 station were used. For the Zuera site, temperature measurements were available from the Casa Perez
179 station located at approximately 10 km west of the study area whereas precipitation data were
180 obtained from an automatic rain gauge installed roughly at the center of the Zuera08 fire perimeter.
181 Since the burned sites were located at different altitudes compared to the meteorological station the
182 temperatures were adjusted with the environmental lapse rate (i.e. $-2^{\circ}\text{C} / 300\text{ m}$). For the Alaskan
183 sites meteorological data were available from the Delta Junction station located within a 45 km
184 radius of the fires (see Table 2). Accumulated precipitation (AcPp) in mm was computed taking into
185 account the last five days before acquisition.

186 At the Zuera site, all images were acquired under dry conditions except the full polarimetric
187 ALOS PALSAR dataset (2009.04.28), as shown in Table 2. At the Delta Junction site, low
188 precipitations were recorded during the acquisition of the first ALOS PALSAR image ($< 1\text{ mm}$) and
189 during the previous days ($< 0.5\text{ mm}$) whereas no precipitation was recorded at the acquisition of the
190 second image.

191 IV. Methods

192 The lack of long-term systematically archived data for most of the SAR frequencies and
193 polarizations conditioned the analysis. In addition, field assessment of the current forest status was
194 available only for the Mediterranean site and the number of samples was not sufficient for a
195 thorough statistical analysis. Therefore, we focused the work on the assessment of radar sensitivity
196 to forest regrowth by means of burns of different age using single date imagery. The time since burn

197 (interpreted as forest age) was used as a quantitative parameter since it is strongly related to forest
198 structure properties (e.g. biomass, tree height, basal area etc.) The relatively small study areas
199 offered homogeneous forest conditions and guaranteed that SAR data were not affected by possible
200 spatial heterogeneities of the environmental conditions.

201 Five fire scars larger than 250 ha were the main focus of the study at the Zuera site. In addition,
202 two smaller fire perimeters (burns from 2001 and 2006) were included (for signature analysis) to
203 cover the last decade. For the Delta Junction site, nine fire scars were selected for the analysis
204 (Table 1). Fire scar selection was carried out taking into account size, vegetation type (scrublands,
205 open forests and woody wetlands were eliminated), fire recurrence (sites repeatedly affected by fire
206 were eliminated), availability of a larger fire scar from the same year, obvious human intervention
207 and availability of the SAR data at all frequencies (Zuera site only).

208 To reduce pixel wise noise of backscatter and coherence measurements the analysis was
209 conducted on samples produced by averaging over several pixel values. The large fire scars and the
210 rather flat topography at the Delta Junction site allowed the generation of contiguous plots (1 ha)
211 using a systematic grid spaced at 600 m. For the Zuera site, the study was carried out using a set of
212 random plots, so called pseudo-plots. Pseudo-plots were generated by averaging inside each burn
213 random pixels of similar slope and aspect with respect to the radar viewing geometry. The
214 generation of pseudo-plots was considered due to the rough topography in most of the studied burns.
215 Changes in local topography greatly influenced the radar signal at Zuera site when analyzing burn
216 severity (Tanase et al. 2010b; Tanase et al. 2010c). To avoid bias related to size, only pseudo-plots
217 containing a constant number of pixels were considered. Nine pixel per pseudo-plot (0.55 ha)
218 appeared to be optimal for the selected spatial resolution (25 m) of the geocoded images (Tanase et
219 al. 2009).

220 For the Delta Junction site, plots with large difference (>0.15) between maximum and minimum
221 NDVI values were discarded due to the increased probability of containing different land cover
222 types. A threshold on NDVI was used to eliminate non-forest pixels thus assuring pseudo-plots
223 homogeneity for the Mediterranean site. In total 652 plots were analyzed at Delta Junction site (15
224 to 250 depending on the burn size) whereas around 2700 pseudo-plots were analyzed at Zuera site,
225 depending on how much of the investigated fires were covered by the SAR dataset. For the Zuera
226 site, the pseudo-plots were clustered into 5°-wide intervals of local incidence angle. As a result,
227 between 15 and 100 pseudo-plots were available for the analysis in each interval. For the small size
228 fires (i.e. 2001 and 2006), the total number of pseudo-plots was small, i.e. between 10 and 25. Since

229 these fires were located on rather flat terrain, most of the pseudo-plots belonged only to one or two
230 local incidence angle intervals.

231 To have a reference on the forest regrowth status, the Mediterranean site was visited near the time
232 of SAR image acquisitions. Since vegetation conditions inside each fire scar were rather
233 homogeneous, two to three points per scar were used for the assessment of vegetation cover fraction
234 and the average tree height and diameter. The cover fraction of the vegetation layers was visually
235 estimated at each plot on a 15 m radius. For trees taller than 2 m, the diameter (D) was measured at
236 breast height whereas for the smaller trees the diameter was measured at half of their height. For the
237 small size fire scars the entire area was visible from the assessed points. For larger burns vegetation
238 conditions assessed at the sampling points were validated by exploring the remaining fire perimeter.
239 Vegetation layers present at Zuera site consisted of herbs and low shrubs less than 1 m tall for the
240 most recent fires, shrubs and small trees up to 5 m tall, and trees up to 15 m tall for the oldest fires.
241 A short description of the average vegetation status at each burn is presented in **Table 3** whereas
242 **Fig. 2** illustrates vegetation development phases found at some of the assessed points. No field data
243 were available for Delta Junction site. Post-fire vegetation is shown in **Fig. 3** for three of the
244 analyzed fires.

245 Descriptive statistics were used to analyze backscatter and coherence sensitivity to forest age. To
246 minimize the effect of topography the analysis was carried out by 5° groups of local incidence angle
247 for the Zuera site. This interval provided optimal sampling rate for the study of the local incidence
248 angle effects on the backscatter of burned areas in sloped terrain in the case of TerraSAR-X (Tanase
249 et al. 2010a). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to assess the possibility to discern between
250 forest recovery stages using mean values of SAR backscatter and coherence, for fire scars larger
251 than 200 ha. Pair wise comparison using Games-Howell test (Games and Howel 1976) provided
252 information on the significantly different mean values. This test was used because it does not
253 assume equal variances, the sample size were unequal and the homogeneity of variance assumption
254 was violated in the ANOVA analysis. The smaller burns (i.e. less than 200 ha) were not included in
255 the analysis due to the small number of samples.

256 V. Results and discussion

257 A. Signature analysis

258 The signal backscattered from forests is the result of complex interactions between microwave
259 electromagnetic energy and the ground and vegetation scattering components (Richards et al. 1987).
260 It depends on the amount and geometric properties of vegetation on site as well as soil dielectric and

261 geometric (roughness) properties on one hand (Dobson et al. 1992a; Imhoff 1995) and on the radar
262 frequency, polarization and look direction on the other hand (Imhoff 1995). With regard to the
263 frequencies considered in this study, X-band waves mostly interact with leaves/needles, twigs and
264 small branches, C-band waves with leaves and small and secondary branches whereas L-band waves
265 interact mostly with primary braches and tree trunks (Toan et al. 1992).

266 A.1. SAR backscatter

267 Plots of mean backscatter (HH and HV polarization) are presented as a function of the local
268 incidence angle for each SAR frequency in Figs. 4 and 5 for the Zuera site. Flat areas correspond to
269 local incidence angles around 25°. Slopes oriented towards the sensor correspond to local incidence
270 angles smaller than 25° whereas slopes oriented away from the sensor correspond to local incidence
271 angles larger than 25°. The average backscatter of the small size fires is represented by the filled
272 symbols whereas the average backscatter of unburned areas (NB) is represented by the grey circles.
273 The standard error of the mean is given in Tables 4 and 5 for some of the local incidence angle
274 intervals. Regardless of the incidence angle, X- and C-band HH polarized backscatter increased for
275 the most recent burns with respect to the older forest (e.g. unburned, 1952 and 1970 burns) (Fig. 4a
276 and 4b) whereas at HV polarization the backscatter decreased (Fig. 5a and 5b). The increase of
277 backscatter at HH polarization was explained by the larger ground component contribution to the
278 total scattering due to the diminishing attenuation layer (forest canopy). At HV polarization, the
279 reduced volume scattering of the young forest reduced the total scattering in recently burned areas.
280 The dynamic range of the X-band backscatter from unburned to recently burned forest (2008) was
281 low (1-2 dB in flat areas) for both polarizations and decreased to 1 dB for the largest incidence
282 angles. For small local incidence angles it reached up to 4 dB for HH polarization (Fig 4a). Stronger
283 sensitivity to changes in forest structure was observed at C-band. The dynamic range between
284 unburned forest and the most recent burn (2008) was around 3 dB in flat areas for both polarizations
285 (Fig. 4b and 5b). For small incidence angles the difference increased up to 7 dB whereas for large
286 incidence angles it decreased to 1 dB for HH polarization. C-band HV polarized backscatter
287 dynamic range was relatively constant over the entire range of incidence angles. The decreasing
288 ground component contribution to the total backscatter explained the decrease of dynamic range for
289 HH polarization with increasing incidence angle at both X- and C-band. Generally, X- and C-band
290 backscatter difference between unburned forest and different stages of forest regrowth was low
291 except for the most recent burns (one to seven years after fire) where the regrowth was negligible.
292 Burned trees still present inside the 2008 fire perimeter increased C-band cross-polarized

293 backscatter when compared to 2001 and 2006 burns from which the dead trees had been removed
294 before the acquisition of the Envisat ASAR image.

295 The largest difference of the backscatter coefficient between forest regrowth stages was
296 observed at L-band. Figs. 4c and 5c illustrate L-band average backscatter of the PLR data
297 (2009.04.28) since it was acquired at similar incidence angle as for X- and C-band. At L-band, the
298 backscatter decreased for decreasing forest age because of the thinner vegetation slab which reduced
299 volume scattering component. The PALSAR image was however acquired during precipitation,
300 which influenced the backscattering coefficient, especially at HH polarization. For slopes oriented
301 towards the sensor, the backscatter differences between forest regrowth stages were not evident (Fig.
302 4c). On slopes oriented away from the sensor the proportion of backscattering from the forest floor
303 plays a smaller role which allowed for an increased dynamic range (approximately 4 dB) from
304 unburned to recently burned forests. At HV polarization, rainfall affected less the backscatter, with
305 measurements presenting larger dynamic range (around 7 dB) with respect to the HH case. As for C-
306 band, the backscatter coefficient was sensitive to the burned trees still standing on site (2008 burn).

307 Fig. 6 illustrates the HH and HV backscatter as a function of the forest age for the two sites, for
308 PALSAR FBD data acquired at 34.3° look angle. Because of the flat topography at Delta Junction,
309 the analysis is focused only on flat terrain. Horizontal lines represent the average backscatter of
310 unburned (NB) areas. Higher values were obtained for the Alaskan site at HH polarization most
311 probably due to the higher soil moisture specific for the boreal environment. At HV polarization the
312 backscatter mean values were similar due to the lower influence of the ground backscattering
313 component. The most obvious difference between the two sites is the lower backscatter values
314 observed at Zuera during the first years after the fire, which was explained by the different type of
315 post-fire management. Spanish administration usually removes the burned standing trees after fire
316 whereas in boreal forest trees are left at on site. Thus, the backscatter from boreal burns contains a
317 significant component of the remaining vegetation whereas in Mediterranean burns this component
318 is usually missing. This explanation was supported by the backscatter levels observed for Zuera
319 2008 burn scar (where trees had not been removed before image acquisition) which were closer to
320 the values observed at Delta Junction. The smaller dynamic range between mature and young forests
321 (3 dB for HH and 5 dB for HV polarization) with respect to Zuera could be explained by the higher
322 variability of forest structure and soil moisture typical of the boreal environment. At the Zuera site,
323 increased dynamic range (6 dB for HH and 10 dB for HV polarization) was observed for the FBD
324 data acquired under dry conditions when compared to PLR data, which had been acquired during

325 rainfall. The larger dynamic range could be also the consequence of the shallower look direction of
326 the FBD mode with respect to the PLR mode.

327 A.2. Interferometric coherence

328 Figs. 7 and 8 illustrate co- and cross-polarized coherence trends for the Zuera site. Regardless of
329 the range of local incidence angles, lower coherence was observed with increasing forest age at X-
330 (HH and HV) and C-band (HH). The standard error of the mean is given in Tables 4 and 5. The
331 highest coherence values were recorded for the most recent burns which presented little or no
332 vegetation cover. The interactions of the high frequency waves with the forest canopy explained the
333 low values obtained in areas of significant forest regrowth. It is interesting to note that the presence
334 of burned standing trees on the 2008 fire site was sufficient to cause decorrelation of the signal
335 almost completely at X-band (Fig. 7a and 8a). At L-band, the coherence showed a completely
336 opposite trend (Fig. 7c and 8c). High coherence was observed for older burns while for the most
337 recent fires the coherence was significantly lower (see also Fig. 9). At the time of acquisition of the
338 PALSAR data, the environmental conditions had been dry for a long period. This caused the upper
339 part of the canopy to be rather transparent to the impinging microwave. Furthermore, Mediterranean
340 pines are stiff trees so that typical decorrelating agents in forests (wind, moisture changes) are not
341 playing a significant role and the coherence is preserved. Yet unclear is the low coherence of recent
342 fires which were characterized primarily by shrub vegetation. Drying of the soil in between the two
343 image acquisitions (46 days) can be considered a plausible explanation; nonetheless, we did not
344 have direct evidence of this. The decreasing trend of coherence with local incidence angle was
345 observed at all frequencies especially for recent burns and was related to the smaller ground
346 component for the slopes oriented away from the sensor.

347 At the Delta Junction site, the L-band coherence decreased with increasing forest age due to the
348 increased vegetation cover (Fig 9). Both polarizations presented similar trends with lower values
349 being recorded at HV polarization due to the predominant contribution to the coherence from the
350 forest canopy. The coherence was overall low because of the 46-days interval between acquisitions.
351 In the boreal zone, the environmental conditions during summer months are prone to rapid changes
352 which cause strong temporal decorrelation in interferograms spanning several weeks. Long periods
353 of stable environmental conditions, as shown in this article for the Zuera site or in (Thiel et al. 2009)
354 for Siberian forest, instead preserve coherence.

355 *B. Statistical analysis*

356 The analysis of variance helped understanding the potential of SAR data to monitor forest
357 regrowth status. For the Zuera site, Table 4 illustrates backscatter and coherence response for three
358 intervals of local incidence angle corresponding to the main type of relief orientation with respect to
359 the radar viewing geometry: *i*) slopes tilted towards the sensor, *ii*) flat or nearly flat areas and *iii*)
360 slopes tilted away from the sensor. The mean values and the standard error are presented for the
361 large fire scars at each SAR frequency. Due to the rather flat topography, the statistics for the area
362 affected by fire in 1970 are presented only for the flat terrain class. For the Delta Junction site, the
363 analysis was carried out considering only the flat terrain conditions. The results from Delta Junction
364 sites are presented in Table 5.

365 For simplicity we grouped the burn scars into the same regrowth phase when the difference in
366 mean backscatter or interferometric coherence between chronological burns was less than 1 dB and
367 0.1 units respectively. We considered a mean backscatter difference of less than 1 dB between two
368 consecutive burns impractical for differentiation of the regrowth phase. The threshold was based on
369 the highest standard error (see Tables 4 and 5) for a confidence interval of 99%. Residual speckle
370 was negligible since the statistical analysis was carried out over several thousands of the original
371 pixels (multi-look processing, pseudo-plots averaging and analysis at fire scar level). Therefore, it
372 was reasonable to assume that the variability inside a given burn corresponded mostly to differences
373 in forest regrowth. Similar reasoning was applied for the coherence analysis. The results from the
374 pair-wise comparison are coded by letters. Average backscatter/coherence for fire scars sharing the
375 same letter is not significantly different, (statistical significance level $p < 0.05$).

376 *B.1. Zuera site*

377 The analysis of variance for the backscatter coefficient revealed statistically significant
378 differences between stages of forest regrowth at all frequencies, polarizations and slope orientations
379 (Table 4). Nevertheless, some of these differences were considered of impractical use. For X-band
380 HH polarization data, only the 2008 burn, for which the mean backscatter was up to 3 dB higher
381 with respect to the other burns, was identified with sufficient confidence in all slope conditions. It is
382 important to note that the 2008 burn represented the case of a recently burned forest with tree stems
383 standing on site rather than the case of a forest regrowth phase. The removal of burned tree stems
384 after fire changes completely the scattering mechanism of the regrowth areas which afterwards are
385 dominated by low shrubs and herbs, hence the result can be considered more as a particular case of
386 burn conditions than a state of forest regrowth. The small dynamic range from unburned to recently
387 burned sites observed at X-band HV polarization indicated limited usefulness despite the

388 statistically significant differences found between some of the regrowth phases. C-band data showed
389 increased discrimination potential for both polarizations. Young forest (1995 burn) was consistently
390 discerned from older forests at HH polarization on slopes looking towards the sensor and flat areas
391 whereas for slopes looking away from the sensor only the 2008 burn was identified. The mean
392 backscatter difference with respect to the older forests varied between 1 and 4 dB depending on
393 slope orientation. At HV polarization, only the most recent burn (2008) was reliably differentiated
394 for all slopes; the average backscatter difference with respect to older burns was between 1 and 2
395 dB. The largest number of forest regrowth phases was differentiated at L-band. Five groups were
396 consistently separated at HH and HV polarization and for all slope orientations. Each individual
397 burn was separated with the exception of the oldest fire scars from 1952 and 1970. The average
398 backscatter difference between consecutive groups was larger than the 1 dB limit. Only for slopes
399 tilted towards the sensor at HH polarization, the differentiation potential of L-band was lower.

400 Statistically significant differences were found between forest regrowth phases when analyzing
401 the interferometric coherence at all frequencies, polarizations and slope conditions. However, the
402 small dynamic range (< 0.2) did not allow reliable identification among different phases of forest
403 regrowth at C- and L-band due to the small variation among individual burns (0.03-0.05). The only
404 exception was the 2008 fire scar where the forest floor provided a stable scattering scenario not
405 greatly influenced by the remaining burned trees. At X-band, the burned trees present within 2008
406 burn were sufficient to completely decorrelate the signal. The proximity to the bias level (i.e. 0.1) of
407 the X-band cross-polarized coherence, regardless of the date of the fire, implied that forest regrowth
408 stages could not be discriminated.

409 B.2. Delta Junction site

410 The analysis of variance produced less obvious results due to smaller time interval between fires,
411 slower regrowth rates and larger variability of the boreal forest in terms of structure, species and
412 moisture conditions (Table 5). Thus, most of the burns pertained to at least two groups in the pair-
413 wise comparison illustrating the transitional nature of the forest regrowth. Three regrowth phases
414 could be differentiated at HH polarization using backscatter information: *i*) unburned forest and
415 1947 burn, *ii*) 1969, 1971 and 1979 burns and *iii*) 1987, 1994, 1998 and 1999 burns; whereas for HV
416 polarization a fourth regrowth phase (1987 burn) was identified as well. These regrowth phases
417 corresponded largely to the decade of burn suggesting temporally consistent traits. As for Zuera, the
418 interferometric coherence showed low discrimination potential for forest regrowth. Statistically
419 significant differences were found between burns but their use for operational application appears to

420 be limited by the small variability of the coherence among individual burns. Only the unburned
421 forests were reliably identified at HH polarization since their mean coherence was significantly
422 lower.

423 C. Regrowth dynamics of SAR and optical data

424 To assess the capability of a remote sensing parameter to monitor forest regrowth, the relative
425 difference of the remote sensing parameter (e.g. backscatter) of a fire-affected area with respect to
426 the unburned conditions is here introduced. We will refer to this quantity as percentage of change.

$$427 \quad \%_{change} = \frac{\bar{x}_{NB} - \bar{x}_{fire}}{\bar{x}_{NB}} * 100 \quad (1)$$

428 In (1), \bar{x}_{NB} represents the value of the remote sensing parameter for unburned conditions
429 whereas \bar{x}_{fire} represents the corresponding value for a specific fire scar. Since it was shown in this
430 Section that the SAR parameter most sensitive to regrowth is L-band HV backscatter, the analysis
431 will be restricted to this parameter. In addition, we consider the percentage of change for the most
432 widely used parameter for monitoring vegetation recovery, i.e. NDVI.

433 The percentage of change with respect to the unburned forest is presented as a function of time
434 from the fire event for L-band HV backscatter and NDVI in Fig. 10. For clarity reasons, the two
435 parameters are represented on opposite sides of the zero change line. The change in backscatter was
436 computed using the average of the plots located in flat areas whereas for optical data all plots were
437 used when averaging for a given fire scar. Mature unburned forests were represented on the zero
438 change line. For Zuera site, the average age of the forest (65 years) was used to estimate the fire-
439 return interval whereas for interior Alaska the fire regime of *Picea mariana* dominated forests was
440 previously estimated between 80 (Hu et al. 2006) and 120 (Kasischke et al. 2002) years. There is a
441 certain lag between forest age at the Zuera and the Delta Junction site due to the different date of the
442 last burns.

443 Fig. 10 shows that the percentage of change for L-band HV backscatter and NDVI decreased
444 with forest age during the first years. After a certain age, the trend flattened, indicating that the
445 signal had reached values similar to those of mature forest. At the Zuera site, the loss of sensitivity
446 of the NDVI metric occurred approximately 15 years after the disturbance. This loss corresponded
447 to the increased canopy cover of the regenerating forest with the age (Table 3). The NDVI
448 percentage of change for 20 years old forests (1986 burn) was negligible when compared to mature
449 forests since the forest canopy fraction reached relatively high levels (70-80%). On the contrary, the
450 L-band HV backscatter percentage of change reached the level of mature forest values

451 approximately 40 to 50 years after disturbance since the recovery of forest structure requires longer
452 periods to complete. The comparative analysis of Table 3 and Fig. 10 highlighted the
453 correspondence between the evolution of the forest cover fraction and NDVI percentage of change
454 on one hand and of the forest structural parameters (diameter and height) and L-band SAR
455 percentage of change on the other hand. For the slower growing boreal forests, NDVI reached pre-
456 fire values approximately 30 years after burn whereas the L-band cross-polarized backscatter needed
457 approximately 60 years. Fig. 10 also shows that the radar data were sensitive to the trees remaining
458 on site after fire. If burned trees are not removed, the backscatter from recent fire scars may be
459 confused with forest regrowth especially during the first years (e.g. 2008 burn at Zuera).

460 To evaluate the association strength between forest age and the percentage of change with respect
461 to unburned forest, a logarithmic model was fitted to the measurements (Fig. 10). The 2008 burn at
462 the Zuera site was excluded since it represented an atypical phase which usually disappears past the
463 second year after disturbance. At both sites the percentage of change for the L-band HV backscatter
464 showed similar trends, suggesting consistent behavior over different environments. Fig. 11
465 illustrates a comparison of the values predicted by the two logarithmic functions. As reference we
466 considered the 1:1 line, indicating perfect correspondence between trends. Fig. 11 shows that
467 regrowth trends are similar during the first years after fire (i.e. for the highest percentage of change).
468 The slower growth rate of the boreal forest is revealed by the additional time needed to reach pre-
469 fire forest structure when compared to Mediterranean forests. When the Mediterranean forest has
470 reached the level of maturity after 65 years (0 % change), at Delta Junction the forest still needs to
471 recover about 10% of the pre-fire structure for which it would need approximately 30 additional
472 years when compared to Zuera pine forests.

473 VI. Conclusions

474 The properties of multi-frequency SAR backscatter and interferometric coherence from
475 Mediterranean and boreal forests affected by fire were investigated with the aim of assessing the
476 potential of active microwave remote sensing for forest regrowth monitoring. A comparison with
477 NDVI index was carried out to establish the advantages and limitations of SAR data with respect to
478 optical sensors. For Mediterranean forests, the L-band SAR backscatter allowed the best
479 differentiation of regrowth phases (five phases for six dates) whereas at X- and C-band the
480 backscatter was less sensitive to modification in forest structure due to the rapid saturation of the
481 signal. For boreal forest, three different regrowth phases could be discerned with L-band HH
482 backscatter data, whereas four phases were separated using HV polarized backscatter. At both test

483 sites, co- and cross-polarized coherence presented weak sensitivity to the different forest regrowth
484 phases, separation being possible only for the most recent burns (<15 years after fire).

485 Analysis of the NDVI in terms of percentage of change with respect to unburned forests in the
486 case of Mediterranean pine forest showed saturation at about 10-20 years after disturbance provided
487 that forest cover recovery is not hindered by other factors (e.g. recurrent fires). For boreal forest, the
488 optical based index reached pre-fire levels within 30 years after fire. L-band SAR backscatter
489 provided much larger monitoring intervals of forest regrowth: around 45 years for Mediterranean
490 and 60 years for boreal forests. Therefore, L-band SAR cross-polarized data appears more suitable
491 to differentiate among forest regrowth stages when compared to optical based indices. The
492 usefulness of SAR data for regrowth monitoring is further supported by the independence from solar
493 illumination and visibility. In addition, the seasonal variability of the L-band backscatter is very
494 small (Santoro et al. 2009) which strengthens the validity of the results here showed. At high
495 latitudes, the availability of usable optical images is scarce due to frequent clouds. Only six images
496 with modest cloud cover were available for Delta Junction site during the vegetation season between
497 1999 and 2009 from which just one was cloud free over all burns.

498 At Zuera site the study took advantage of the minor human intervention and the vigorous forest
499 recovery which allowed almost ideal conditions for natural regeneration that could not be met in
500 other regions. In addition, repeatedly burned areas could present different regeneration patterns
501 especially when fires occur at short time intervals, before forests reach maturity. Therefore, the
502 temporal recovery trend registered for the Zuera site could take longer in forests exposed to harsh
503 environment or when fire cycle is short.

504 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

505 This work has been financed by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Education and the
506 European Social Fund: FPI grant BES-2006-11684 and projects CGL2005-04863 and CGL2008-
507 01083. TerraSAR-X data were provided by Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR) in
508 the framework of LAN0464 project. ASAR and PALSAR data were provided by European Space
509 Agency (ESA) in the framework of C1P.5446 project.

510 REFERENCES

- 511 Bourgeau-Chavez, L.L., Harrell, P.A., Kasischke, E.S., & French, N.H.F. (1997). The detection and mapping of Alaskan
512 wildfires using a spaceborne imaging radar system. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 18, 355-373
- 513 Bourgeau-Chavez, L.L., Kasischke, E.S., Brunzell, S., & Mudd, J.P. (2002). Mapping fire scars in global boreal forests
514 using imaging radar data. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 23, 4211-4234

- 515 Buhk, C., Götzenberger, L., Wesche, K., Gómez, P.S., & Hensen, I. (2006). Post-fire regeneration in a Mediterranean
516 pine forest with historically low fire frequency. *Acta Oecologica*, 30, 288-289
- 517 Clemente, R.H., Cerrillo, R.M.N., & Gitas, I.Z. (2009). Monitoring post-fire regeneration in Mediterranean ecosystems
518 by employing multitemporal satellite imagery. *International Journal of Wildland Fire*, 18, 648-658
- 519 Cuevas-Gonzalez, M., Gerard, F., Balzter, H., & Riaño, D. (2009). Analysing forest recovery after wildfire disturbance
520 in boreal Siberia using remotely sensed vegetation indices. *Global Change Biology*, 15, 561-577
- 521 Díaz-Delgado, R., Lloret, F., & Pons, X. (2003). Influence of fire severity on plant regeneration by means of remote
522 sensing imagery. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 24, 1751-1763
- 523 Díaz-Delgado, R., Lloret, F., Pons, X., & Terradas, J. (2002). Satellite evidence of decreasing resilience in
524 Mediterranean plant communities after recurrent wildfires. *Ecology*, 83, 2293-2303
- 525 Díaz-Delgado, R., & Pons, X. (2001). Spatial patterns of forest fires in Catalonia (NE Spain) along the period 1975-
526 1995. Analysis of vegetation recovery after fire. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 147, 67-74
- 527 Dobson, M., L, P., K, S., FT, U., & T, S. (1992a). Preliminary analisis of ERS-1 SAR for forest ecosystme studies.
528 *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 30, 203-211
- 529 Dobson, M.C., Ulaby, T., Le Toan, T., Beaudoin, A., & Kasischke, E.S. (1992b). Dependence of radar backscatter on
530 coniferous forest biomass. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 30 412-415
- 531 Games, P.A., & Howel, J.F. (1976). Pairwise Multiple Comparison Procedures with Unequal N's and/or Variances: A
532 Monte Carlo Study. *Journal of Education and Behavioral Statistics*, 1, 113-125
- 533 Goetz, S.J., Sun, M., Baccini, A., & Beck, P.S.A. (2010). Synergistic use of spaceborne lidar and optical imagery for
534 assessing forest disturbance: An Alaska case study. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 115, 1-14
- 535 Henry, M.C., & Hope, A.S. (1998). Monitoring post-burn recovery of chaparral vegetation in southern California using
536 multi-temporal satellite data. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 19, 3097-3107
- 537 Hu, F.S., Brubaker, L.B., Gavin, D.G., Higuera, P.E., Lynch, J.A., Rupp, T.S., & Tinner, W. (2006). How Climate and
538 Vegetation Influence the fire Regime of the Alaskan Boreal Biome: The Holocene Perspective. *Mitigation and
539 Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 11, 829-846
- 540 Imhoff, M.L. (1995). Radar Backscatter and Biomass Saturation: Ramifications for Global Biomass Inventory. *IEEE
541 Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 33, 511-518
- 542 Kasischke, E.S., & Johnstone, J.F. (2005). Variation in post-fire organic layer thickness in a black spruce forest complex
543 in Interior Alaska and its effects on soil temperature and moisture. *Canadian Journal of Remote Sensing*, 35, 2164-
544 2177
- 545 Kasischke, E.S., Williams, D., & Barry, D. (2002). Analysis of the patterns of large fires in the boreal forest region of
546 Alaska. *International Journal of Wildland Fire*, 11, 131-144
- 547 Liew, S.C., Kwok, L.K., Padmanabhan, K., Lim, O.K., & Lim, H. (1999). Delineating Land/Forest Fire Burnt Scars with
548 ERS Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 26, 2409-2412
- 549 Marchetti, M., Ricotta, C., & Volpe, F. (1995). A qualitative approach to the mapping of postfire regrowth in
550 Mediterranean vegetation with Landsat- TM. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 16, 2487-2494
- 551 Minchella, A., Del Frate, F., Capogna, F., Anselmi, S., & Manes, F. (2009). Use of multitemporal SAR data for
552 monitoring vegetation recovery of Mediterranean burned areas. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 113, 588-597
- 553 Notivol, E., Cabanillas, A., González, R., & Revuelta, C. (2005). Caracterización de masas naturales de pino carrasco
554 (*Pinus halepensis* Mill.) en la depresión del Ebro. In, *IV Congreso Forestal Español* (p. 299). Zaragoza: Sociedad
555 Española de Ciencias Forestales
- 556 Patterson, M.W., & Yool, S.R. (1998). Mapping Fire-Induced Vegetation Mortality Using Landsat Thematic Mapper
557 Data: A Comparison of Linear Transformation Techniques. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 65, 132-142
- 558 Pausas, J.G., Gimeno, T., & Vallejo, R. (Eds.) (2002). *Fire severity and pine regeneration in the eastern Iberian
559 Peninsula*: Millpres, Rotterdam
- 560 Pérez-Cabello, F. (2002). *Paisajes forestales y fuego en el Prepirineo occidental oscense. Un modelo regional de
561 reconstrucción ambiental*. Zaragoza. Zaragoza

- 562 Richards, J.A., Sun, G.-Q., & Simonett, D.S. (1987). L-Band Radar Backscatter Modeling of Forest Stands. *IEEE*
563 *Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 4, 487-498
- 564 Rignot, E.J., Williams, C.L., Way, J., & Viereck, L.A. (1994). Mapping of forest types in Alaskan boreal forests using
565 SAR imagery. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 32, 1051-1059
- 566 Rouse, J.W., Haas, R.H., Schell, J.A., & Deering, D.W. (1973). Monitoring vegetation systems in the Great Plains with
567 ERTS In, *Third ERTS Symposium* (pp. 309-317)
- 568 Ruecker, G., & Siegert, F. (2000). Burn scar mapping and fire damage assessment using ERS-2 Sar images in East
569 Kalimantan, Indonesia. *International Archives of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 33, 1286-1293
- 570 Santoro, M., Fransson, J.E.S., Eriksson, L.E.B., Magnusson, M., Ulander, L.M.H., & Olsson, H. (2009). Signatures of
571 ALOS PALSAR L-Band Backscatter in Swedish Forest. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 47,
572 4001 - 4019
- 573 Siegert, F., & Ruecker, G. (2000). Use of multitemporal ERS-2 SAR images for identification of burned scars in south-
574 east Asian tropical rainforest. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 21, 831-837
- 575 Sun, G.Q., Rocchio, L., Masek, J., Williams, D., & Ranson, K.J. (2002). Characterization of forest recovery from fire
576 using Landsat and SAR data. In, *Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium, 2002. IGARSS '02. Proceedings. 2002*
577 *IEEE International* (pp. 1076-1078). Toronto, Canada
- 578 Takeuchi, S., & Yamada, S. (2002). Monitoring of Forest Fire Damage by Using JERS-1 InSAR. In, *Geoscience and*
579 *Remote Sensing Symposium, 2002. IGARSS '02. Proceedings. 2002 IEEE International* (pp. 3290-3292). Toronto,
580 Canada
- 581 Tanase, M.A., Pérez-Cabello, F., Riva, J.d.l., & Santoro, M. (2010a). TerraSAR-X data for burn severity evaluation in
582 Mediterranean forests on sloped terrain. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 48, 917-929
- 583 Tanase, M.A., Riva, J.d.l., Santoro, M., Toan, T.L., & Perez-Cabello, F. (2010b). Sensitivity of X-, C- and L-band SAR
584 backscatter to fire severity in mediterranean pine forests. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 48,
585 3663-3675
- 586 Tanase, M.A., Santoro, M., Riva, J.d.l., & Pérez-Cabello, F. (2009). Backscatter properties of multitemporal TerraSAR-
587 X data and the effects of influencing factors on burn severity evaluation, in a Mediterranean pine forest. In,
588 *Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium, 2009. IGARSS '09. 2009 IEEE International* (pp. 593-596). Cape
589 Town, South Africa
- 590 Tanase, M.A., Santoro, M., Wegmüller, U., Riva, J.d.l., & Perez-Cabello, F. (2010c). Properties of X-, C- and L-band
591 repeat-pass interferometric SAR coherence in Mediterranean pine forests affected by fires. *Remote Sensing of*
592 *Environment*, 114, 2182-2194
- 593 Tapias, R., Gil, L., & Fuentes-Utrilla, P. (2001). Canopy seed banks in Mediterranean pines of southeastern Spain: a
594 comparison between *Pinus halepensis* Mill., *P. pinaster* Ait., *P. nigra* Arn. and *P. pinea* L. *Journal of Ecology*, 89,
595 629-638
- 596 Thiel, C.J., Thiel, C., & Schullius, C.C. (2009). Operational Large-Area Forest Monitoring in Siberia Using ALOS
597 PALSAR Summer Intensities and Winter Coherence. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 47,
598 3993 - 4000
- 599 Toan, T.L., Beaudoin, A., & Guyon, D. (1992). Relating forest biomass to SAR data. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience*
600 *and Remote Sensing*, 30, 403-411
- 601 Ulander, L.M.H. (1996). Radiometric slope correction of synthetic-aperture radar images. *IEEE Transactions on*
602 *Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 34, 1115-1122
- 603 Viedma, Melia, J., Segarra, D., & Garcia-Haro, J. (1997). Modeling Rates of Ecosystem Recovery after Fires by Using
604 Landsat TM Data. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 61, 383-398
- 605 Viereck, L.A., Dyrness, C.T., Van Cleve, K., & Foote, M.J. (1983). Vegetation, soils, and forest productivity in selected
606 forest types in interior Alaska. *Canadian Journal of Remote Sensing*, 13, 703-720
- 607 Vila, J.P.S., & Barbosa, P. (2010). Post-fire vegetation regrowth detection in the Deiva Marina region (Liguria-Italy)
608 using Landsat TM and ETM+ data. *Ecological Modelling*, 221, 75-84

- 609 Wagtendonk, J.W.v., Root, R.R., & Key, C.H. (2004). Comparison of AVIRIS and Landsat ETM+ detection capabilities
610 for burn severity. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 92, 397-408
- 611 Wang, Q., Adiku, S., Tenhunen, J., & Granier, A. (2005). On the relationship of NDVI with leaf area index in a
612 deciduous forest site. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 94, 244-255
- 613 Wegmuller, U., & Werner, C.L. (1995). SAR Interferometric Signatures of Forest. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience
614 and Remote Sensing*, 33, 1153-1161
- 615
- 616
- 617

618 Table 1 Fire scars and the affected area computed from the digitized fire perimeters.

619 Forest age is referred to the year of the SAR dataset (see Table 3).

Year	Zuera site		Delta Junction site		
	Burned area (ha)	Forest age	Year	Burned area (ha)	Forest age
1922	1030	87	1947*	2097	60
1952*	2000	57	1951	9387	56
1970*	272	39	1954	7312	53
1979	680	30	1969*	28101	38
1983	25	26	1969b	892	38
1984	29	25	1971*	2150	36
1985	10	24	1979*	13588	28
1986*	303	23	1979b	2518	28
1990	23	19	1979c	1342	28
1994	37	15	1980	3338	27
1994	96	15	1981	8269	26
1995*	3100	14	1984	1233	23
2001*	26	8	1987*	18336	20
2005	30	4	1993*	192	14
2006*	31	3	1994	318	13
2008*	2200	<1	1994*	8904	13
			1995	951	12
			1998*	22045	9
			1999*	7581	8
			2001	44.7	6

* analyzed fires

620

621 Table 2 SAR acquisition date, incidence angle, perpendicular (Pb) and temporal (Tb) baselines, and meteorological conditions at time
622 of acquisition: maximum temperature (Tmax) and minimum temperature (Tmin) in °C and the accumulated precipitations (AcPp).

Area	Sensor	Polarization	Angle	Acquisition date 1	Acquisition date 2	Pb (m)	Tb (days)	AcPp date1	Tmax date1	Tmin date1	AcPp date2	Tmax date2	Tmin date2
Backscatter analysis													
Zuera	TSX	HH,HV	25°	2008.12.24				0	-3	-6			
	ASAR	HH,HV	23°	2009.03.19				0	20	-1			
	PALSAR	all	25°	2009.04.28				3.5*	18	10			
	PALSAR	HH,HV	34°	2009.08.20				0	34	15			
Interferometric coherence analysis													
	TSX	HH,HV	40°	2008.11.16	2008.12.19	231	33	0	14	-2	0	11	4
	ASAR	HH	23°	2009.01.08	2009.02.12	34	35	0.5	0	-6	0.5	10	4
	PALSAR	HH,HV	34°	2009.08.20	2009.10.05	508	46	0	34	15	0	26	11
Backscatter & Interferometric coherence analysis													
Delta Junction	PALSAR	HH,HV	34°	2007.08.15	2007.09.30	483	46	1.3*	24	12	0.1	9	-3

* precipitations registered partially during the day of SAR acquisition

623

624

625 Table 3 Average vegetation conditions for the analyzed fire scars at Zuera site.

Fire	Strata	Cover (%)	Height (m)	D (cm)	Fire	Strata	Cover (%)	Height (m)	D (cm)
Not burned	Herbs	20-70	0.3-1		1995	Herbs	10	0.2-0.3	
	Shrubs	5-60	0.5-2			Shrubs	30-35	0.5-1	
	Trees	40-75	8-12	8-35		Trees	55-65	0.7-2	2-3
1952	Herbs	10	0.2-0.3		2001	Herbs	80	0.2-1	
	Shrubs	20-25	0.7-1.5			Shrubs	10	0.5-1	
	Trees	60-75	8-9	10-25		Trees	5-10	0.5-1	< 3
1970	Herbs	10-20	0.1-0.3		2006	Herbs	70	50-80	
	Shrubs	50-60	0.5-2			Shrubs	5	0.5-0.8	
	Trees	90	3-6	9-16		Trees	N/A	0.1-0.2	< 1
1986	Herbs	10	0.4		2008	Herbs	5-20	0.1-0.3	
	Shrubs	5-10	0.5-1			Shrubs	5-20	0.1-0.3	
	Trees	70-80	1.5-4	3-5		Trees	N/A	8-12	8-35

626

627

628

629
630
631
632
633
634

Table 4 Average properties of the fire scars for different slope orientations. Data represent mean values and their standard error. Letters indicate differences between groups ($p < 0.05$). Zuera site.

Slope orientation		Not burned	1952	1970	1986	1995	2008
Backscatter							
X-band HH	Toward sensor	-11.7 (0.28) a	-11.2 (0.25) a	N/A	-11.2 (0.18) a	-10.8 (0.24) a	-7.6 (0.19) b
	Flat area	-9.4 (0.08) a	-9.3 (0.11) a	-9.9 (0.08) b	-9.5 (0.14) ab	-9.6 (0.14) ab	-7.7 (0.08) c
	Away from sensor	-9.2 (0.05) a	-9.4 (0.05) a	N/A	-10.0 (0.06) b	-9.4 (0.10) a	-8.5 (0.07) c
X-band HV	Toward sensor	-19.1 (0.36) a	-18.7 (0.25) a	N/A	-19.2 (0.18) a	-19.6 (0.22) a	-19.5 (0.21) a
	Flat area	-16.2 (0.06) a	-15.9 (0.11) b	-16.8 (0.05) bc	-16.6 (0.11) b	-17.1 (0.10) cd	-17.1 (0.06) d
	Away from sensor	-14.6 (0.04) a	-14.5 (0.05) a	N/A	-15.2 (0.05) b	-15.2 (0.06) b	-15.7 (0.05) c
C-band HH	Toward sensor	-12.2 (0.37) a	-11.4 (0.22) a	N/A	-11.5 (0.22) a	-9.1 (0.21) b	-4.9 (0.14) c
	Flat area	-11.3 (0.16) a	-11.4 (0.24) a	-11.7 (0.13) a	-11.9 (0.27) a	-10.5 (0.17) b	-7.9 (0.27) c
	Away from sensor	-12.2 (0.14) a	-12.1 (0.13) a	N/A	-12.0 (0.14) a	-11.9 (0.13) a	-11.1 (0.15) b
C-band HV	Toward sensor	-18.0 (0.27) a	-16.8 (0.20) b	N/A	-17.4(0.22) ab	-18.2 (0.22) a	-20.7 (0.20) c
	Flat area	-15.3 (0.14) a	-15.5 (0.24) ab	-16.2 (0.11) bc	-16.0 (0.14) b	-16.6 (0.15) c	-18.4 (0.16) d
	Away from sensor	-15.1 (0.14) ab	-14.6 (0.15) a	N/A	-14.8(0.15) ab	-15.3 (0.12) b	-17.7 (0.12) c
L-band HH*	Toward sensor	-11.9 (0.12) a	-12.5 (0.25) ab	N/A	-12.7 (0.10) b	-13.4 (0.14) c	-13.1 (0.17) bc
	Flat area	-10.8 (0.05) a	-11.4 (0.08) b	-11.7 (0.05) b	-12.1 (0.09) c	-13.7 (0.07) d	-14.4 (0.11) e
	Away from sensor	-9.1 (0.07) a	-9.9 (0.07) b	N/A	-11.2 (0.07) c	-12.5 (0.08) d	-14.1 (0.12) e
L-band HV*	Toward sensor	-16.9 (0.09) a	-18.3 (0.15) b	N/A	-19.8 (0.13) c	-21.7 (0.12) d	-25.0 (0.14) e
	Flat area	-15.0 (0.05) a	-15.8 (0.07) b	-15.8 (0.04) b	-17.0 (0.09) c	-18.7 (0.10) d	-21.8 (0.16) e
	Away from sensor	-13.3 (0.05) a	-14.0 (0.08) b	N/A	-15.0 (0.12) c	-16.9 (0.10) d	-20.9 (0.20) e
Coherence							
X-band HH	Toward sensor	0.17 (0.00) a	0.19 (0.00) b	N/A	0.27 (0.01) c	0.33 (0.00) d	0.34 (0.00) d
	Flat area	0.18 (0.00) a	0.15 (0.00) b	0.22 (0.00) c	0.23 (0.01) c	0.33 (0.01) d	0.31 (0.00) d
	Away from sensor	0.11 (0.00) a	0.10 (0.00) a	N/A	0.13 (0.00) b	0.24 (0.00) c	0.22 (0.00) d
X-band HV	Toward sensor	0.13 (0.00) a	0.13(0.00) a	N/A	0.20 (0.00) b	0.25 (0.00) c	0.18 (0.00) b
	Flat area	0.12 (0.00) a	0.12 (0.00) a	0.14 (0.00) b	0.16 (0.00) c	0.21 (0.00) d	0.17 (0.00) c
	Away from sensor	0.09 (0.00) a	0.09 (0.00) a	N/A	0.09 (0.00) a	0.15 (0.00) b	0.11 (0.00) c
C-band HH	Toward sensor	0.21 (0.01) a	0.22 (0.01) a	N/A	0.21 (0.00) a	0.28 (0.01) b	0.53 (0.01) c
	Flat area	0.18 (0.00) a	0.20 (0.00) b	0.18 (0.00) a	0.19 (0.01) ab	0.28 (0.01) c	0.38 (0.01) d
	Away from sensor	0.12 (0.00) a	0.14 (0.00) a	N/A	0.16 (0.00) b	0.19 (0.00) c	0.24 (0.01) d
L-band HH	Toward sensor	0.77 (0.00) a	0.71 (0.01) b	N/A	0.83 (0.00) c	0.77 (0.00) a	0.72 (0.00) b
	Flat area	0.77 (0.00) a	0.78 (0.00) ab	0.79 (0.00) b	0.84 (0.00) c	0.76 (0.00) d	0.63 (0.00) e
	Away from sensor	0.76 (0.00) a	0.80 (0.00) b	N/A	0.83 (0.00) c	0.76 (0.00) a	0.56 (0.01) d
L-band HV	Toward sensor	0.75 (0.00) a	0.69 (0.01) b	N/A	0.76 (0.00) a	0.69 (0.00) b	0.48 (0.00) c
	Flat area	0.75 (0.00) a	0.76 (0.00) a	0.75 (0.00) a	0.81 (0.00) b	0.71 (0.00) c	0.48 (0.00) d
	Away from sensor	0.73 (0.00) a	0.78 (0.00) b	N/A	0.83 (0.00) c	0.73 (0.00) a	0.41 (0.01) d

* Reported for data not affected by rain (FDB, 2008.08.20, look angle 34°)

635
636
637
638
639
640

Table 5. Average properties of the fire scars. Data represent mean values and their standard error. Letters indicate differences between groups ($p < 0.05$). Delta Junction site.

		NB	1947	1969	1971	1979	1987	1994	1998	1999
Backscatter										
L-band										
HH		-9.0(0.28)a	-9.2(0.12)a	-9.9(0.27)b	-10.4(0.29)b	-10.3(0.16)b	-11.0(0.08)c	-11.9(0.19)c	-11.5(0.10)c	-11.1(0.12)c
HV		-14.7(0.37)a	-15.2(0.18)a	-16.1(0.37)b	-16.8(0.31)b	-16.6(0.14)b	-18.1(0.11)c	-19.9(0.17)d	-19.0(0.09)d	-20.4(0.17)d
Coherence										
L-band										
HH		0.31(0.02)a	0.49(0.02)b	0.46 (0.03)b	0.55(0.01)b	0.50(0.01)b	0.51(0.00)b	0.62(0.01)b	0.56(0.01)b	0.63(0.01)b
HV		0.26(0.02)a	0.36(0.02)a	0.41(0.02)a	0.38(0.02)a	0.27(0.01)a	0.41(0.00)a	0.46(0.01)a	0.43(0.01)a	0.49(0.01)a

641
642
643
644
645
646
647
648
649

650
651
652

653

654
655
656
657
658

Fig. 2 Examples of vegetation recovery at the Zuera site. The pictures were taken during summer 2009

659
660
661
662
663

Fig. 3 Examples of vegetation recovery at the Delta Junction site. The pictures were taken during summer 2008

664
665

Fig. 4 Co-polarized (HH) normalized backscatter coefficient (γ^0) trend as a function of the local incidence angle. X-band 2008.12.24 (a), C-band 2009.01.28 (b) and L-band 2009.04.28 (c). Zuera site.

666
667

Fig. 5 Cross-polarized (HV) normalized backscatter coefficient (γ^0) trend as a function of the local incidence angle. X-band 2008.12.24 (a), C-band 2009.03.19 (b) and L-band 2009.04.28 (c). Zuera site.

668
669

Fig. 6 Average L-band normalized backscatter coefficient (γ^0) as a function of burn age for fire scars located on flat terrain. Delta Junction (2007.08.15) and Zuera (2009.08.20) site. Horizontal lines represent backscatter levels of unburned forests for HH and HV polarizations.

670

Fig. 7 Co-polarized (HH) coherence trend as a function of the local incidence angle. X-band 2008.11.16 / 2008.12.19 (a), C-band 2009.01.08 / 2009.02.12 (b) and L-band 2009.08.20 / 2009.10.05 (c). Zuera site.

Fig. 8 Cross-polarized (HV) coherence trend as a function of the local incidence angle. X-band 2008.11.1 / 2008.12.19 (a) and L-band 2009.08.20 / 2009.10.05 (b). Zuera site.

671
672

Fig. 9 Average L-band coherence as a function of burn age for fire scars located on flat terrain. Delta Junction and Zuera sites. Horizontal lines represent coherence levels of unburned forests for HH and HV polarizations.

673
674

Fig. 10 Forest recovery as seen by L-band SAR and optical based NDVI – percentage of change with respect to the unburned area for Zuera (a) and Delta Junction (b) sites.

675

Fig. 11 Co-plotted model-based percentage of change with respect to the unburned area for Zuera and Delta Junction sites.

676
677
678